

Enabling 5G Indoor Services for Residential Environment using VLC Technology

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Abstract

Visible light communication (VLC) has emerged as a viable complement to traditional radio frequency (RF) based systems and as an enabler for high data rate communications for beyond-5G (B5G) indoor communication systems. In particular, the emergence of new B5G-based applications with quality of service (QoS) requirements and massive connectivity has recently led to research on the required service-levels and the development of improved physical (PHY) layer methods. As part of recent VLC standards development activities, the IEEE has formed the 802.11bb “Light Communications (LC) for Wireless Local Area Networking” standardization group. This paper investigates the network requirements of 5G indoor services such as virtual reality (VR) and high-definition (HD) video for residential environments using VLC. In this paper, we consider such typical VLC scenarios with additional impairments such as light-emitting diode (LED) non-linearity and imperfect channel feedback, and propose hyperparameter-free mitigation techniques using Reproducing Kernel Hilbert Space (RKHS) methods. In this context, we also propose using a direct current biased optical orthogonal frequency division multiplexing (DCO-OFDM)-based adaptive VLC transmission method that uses precomputed bit error rate (BER) expressions for these RKHS-based detection methods and performs adaptive BER-based modulation-order switching. Simulations of channel impulse responses (CIRs) show that the adaptive transmission method provides significantly improved error rate performance, which makes it promising for high data rate VLC-based 5G indoor services.

Keywords: Visible light communication (VLC), ray-tracing, adaptive transmission, 5G services.

1. Introduction

Fifth-generation (5G) wireless networks are currently being deployed in various countries around the world under the 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP) Release 15 standard, and 5G is expected to spawn new services and applications [1]. 5G offers several capabilities and cutting-edge technologies compared to 4G, including Massive Multiple-Input Multiple-Output, Network Functions Virtualization, Software Defined Networking, Edge Computing, Network Slicing, etc. Typical 5G applications are expected to be very large and include Augmented Reality (AR) [2], Virtual Reality (VR) [3], High Definition (HD) video streaming [4], industrial automation, emergency services and automated driving for various industries such as automotive, transportation, healthcare, media and entertainment, and smart cities.

1.1. Motivation

In the context of the above ecosystems, it is commonly noted that the majority of traffic is generated by indoor users. According to [5], 70% of 4G services are used indoors. In addition, industry experts claim that commercial indoor 5G services (such as AR, VR, HD video streaming, etc.) are expected to account for 80% of all services offered. Moreover, traffic density per 100 m² is expected to reach 250 Mbps in 2022. Therefore, 5G networks must be able to support future indoor applications that require 1 connection per m² with a downlink rate of more than 100 Mbps at the cell edge [5]. To this end, operators will need to consider these requirements for their indoor 5G network deployments.

Recently, HD video calling and streaming services (such as Netflix, Orange TV, and Movistar+) and gaming services have become increasingly popular. Indoor VR and HD video services are provided to user equipment (UE), which is mostly static or slow moving. However, traffic usage changes drastically depending on service/application usage as time and space vary. For these applications, the sessions provided to the User Equipment (UE) must be relatively long and connected with a fast wireless connection (e.g., to enable full HD connection) without interruptions or poor audio and video quality, otherwise the UE will experience a lower quality of experience (QoE).

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In addition, the visible light communication (VLC) paradigm leverages common lighting infrastructures for wireless data communication. This paradigm aims to create the ubiquity required for next-generation wireless networks and ultimately enable huge transmission rates by leveraging the entire optical spectrum. Future VLC-based networks will need to adapt to traffic peaks by adjusting transmission parameters accordingly to meet the various service requirements of indoor UEs. In addition, VLC [6] has been shown to be capable of complementing existing wireless connectivity services in radio frequency (RF) bands. In addition, VLC is an emerging technology for short-range wireless access with virtually unlimited unlicensed bandwidth, electromagnetic interference immunity, and low installation cost. In addition, it is well known that VLC can be integrated with the existing lighting infrastructure to serve the dual purpose of illumination and communication simultaneously. Due to the above advantages, VLC has emerged as a powerful complement to its RF counterpart in the context of Beyond-5G (B5G) communication systems.

1.2. Related Works and Main Contributions

In recent years, a large literature on VLC link-adaptation has emerged. In [7], adaptive control of orthogonal frequency division multiplexing (OFDM) modulation order was presented to improve the performance of VLC links. In [7], experimental results showed that by switching the OFDM order from 16 quadrature amplitude modulation (QAM) to quadrature phase shift keying (QPSK), a signal-to-noise-ratio (SNR) of 18 dB can be restored. In addition, it has been shown that the transmission distance in free space can be reduced from 2 m to 1.2 m to increase the effective OFDM subcarriers and the overall data rate. In [8], it was found that asymmetrically clipped optical OFDM (ACO-OFDM) based adaptive modulation provides better spectral efficiency (SE) than DC-biased optical OFDM (DCO-OFDM)-based adaptive modulation.

In [9], an optical code division multiplexing access (OCDMA) combined with a multiuser multiple-input single-output (MISO) technique was proposed for an adaptive M -ary pulse amplitude modulation (M-PAM) scheme to support multiple users. The work in [9] derived a fair power allocation and M-PAM constellation order-assignment methods for users to adapt to various shadowing effects and achieve the desired bit error-rates (BERs). In [10], a nonlinear adaptive algorithm was proposed to correct the nonlinearity of light emitting diode (LED) in a VLC envi-

ronment. In [11], an adaptive algorithm for multiple-input multiple-output (MIMO) OFDM VLC systems was proposed to maximize SE while satisfying a given target BER. Considering that the received power varies significantly depending on the user's location, adaptive luminaire selection was proposed in [12] to improve SE. In [13], an adaptive minimum energy MIMO method is proposed for different room locations for a desired SE and a target BER. In [14], an enhanced adaptive scheme with pairwise coding for the OFDM-VLC system was experimentally demonstrated to further improve the BER performance.

In [15], an adaptive power control strategy was proposed that outperformed gain ratio power allocation, fixed power allocation, and time division multiple access schemes. In [16], a channel adaptive spatial constellation (CASC) was proposed for the MIMO VLC system, where the optimal transmitted signal constellation was determined based on the best channel state. It was also shown that CASC provides significant improvement in error performance over different channels compared to conventional MIMO VLC schemes. In [17], an adaptive system based on switching between spatial modulation (SM), spatial multiplexing (SMUX), repetition code (RC) and adaptive generalized spatial modulation (AGSM) was presented to increase the data rate. In [18], an adaptive precoder scheme was presented to reduce the channel correlation or condition number of MIMO channel matrix and mitigate LED nonlinearity. In [19], a neural network-based adaptive pattern based on the channel conditions was proposed to coordinate the MIMO channels.

Against this background, the main contributions of this paper are briefly outlined below:

- We use a realistic ray-tracing method for channel modeling [20]. In this context, channel impulse responses (CIRs) are obtained for a realistic residential environment where the specifications of user model and man-made objects are fully integrated into the channel model and illumination requirements are also satisfied. Furthermore, physical assumptions such as wavelength-dependent reflection properties, diffuse-specular reflections, measured light sources, and reflection order up to 10 are taken into account.
- The evolving VLC-based 5G wireless networks demand various quality of service (QoS) requirements, e.g., data quality, high reliability, etc. However, it is challenging to meet these requirements simultaneously, which leads to a trade-off between different metrics. In this context, we investigate the design of an adaptive MIMO OFDM VLC system to

enable 5G indoor services in a residential environment. First, we study the DCO-OFDM based adaptive VLC transmission method with intensity modulation and direct detection (IM/DD)¹. scheme that uses precomputed BER expressions and performs adaptive BER-based modulation order switching. Then, the service requirements of 5G indoor services such as data rate and packet loss are considered, which ensures the quality of multimedia applications.

- It is well known that the performance of typical VLC systems degrades due to transmit-side LED nonlinearity and non-negligible intersymbol interference (ISI). In this context, explicit knowledge of the characteristics of these degradations is generally not guaranteed at the receiver. This requires distribution-adaptive signal processing methods such as the Random Fourier Feature (RFF) approaches for generic impairment mitigation. RFF-based receivers have emerged as an attractive signal processing paradigm for impairment-mitigation, and recent works present rigorous analytical guarantees for their near-optimality and universal approximation of these approaches for both VLC and RF scenarios with unknown transmitter side nonlinearity [21–24]. In this paper, we focus on hyperparameter-free post-distortion for O-OFDM and derive relevant parameter values for the kernel sampling distribution. This hyperparameter-free approach makes this method generic for different deployment scenarios or nonlinearity characteristics and reduces the need for dataset-specific kernel-width initialization or concurrent kernel width estimation [22]. Moreover, hyperparameter-free feature maps are known to reduce dependence on accurate initialization of kernel width, which in turn depends on the observation statistics or varies over coherence times/deployment scenarios. It is known that this hyperparameter free map allows generalized channel inversion for a wide class of nonlinearities without the need to know their exact characteristics a priori and without hyperparameter tuning.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. In Section 2 the problem description is elaborated. In Section 3, the channel models for the residential environment are presented. In

¹Heterodyne detection based systems provide better results than IM/DD systems; however, the IM/DD based approaches are advantageous due to their simplicity which is why they are widely used.

Section 4, the proposed adaptive transmission system model is presented and numerical results and discussions are provided. Finally, conclusions are drawn in Section 5.

2. Problem Description

In this paper, we consider an example use case for an indoor scenario where the goal is to provide the network infrastructure with adaptive transmission capabilities to meet increasingly stringent QoS levels for different services. In the considered scenario, we take into account the need for adaptive transmission and the requirements of operators and service providers (depending on Service Level Agreements (SLAs)) on the network infrastructure. In this regard, one of the main contributions of this work is to achieve significantly improved QoS levels from operators or service providers through demand-driven reactive decisions for each service and observations of the infrastructure (e.g., bandwidth, latency, packet loss, etc.). Moreover, the main technical challenge in this paper is to provide adaptive and dynamic transmission strategies that achieve the desired QoS levels of the services considering the available environmental conditions and service requirements.

A general flowchart of the considered scenario is shown in Fig. 1. First, available services (e.g., VR and HD video services) transmit their resource demands to service or infrastructure providers. The services can be operated by service providers, infrastructure providers or third-party providers (e.g., Amazon). Depending on the SLAs between these providers, infrastructure and service level measurements received directly from the network infrastructure and services, as well as service requests are sent to the proposed adaptive transmission unit. In this unit, the necessary adjustments and adaptive transmission are performed using the methodology proposed in Section 4. Later, these parameters are returned to the network infrastructure to perform appropriate actions. Note that Fig. 1 is an example of a closed-loop automation scenario where continuous and adaptive adjustments are made to the transmission parameters based on network and service level observations as well as the service requirements.

Figure 1: The flowchart of a closed-loop automation scenario with adaptive transmission.

3. Channel Models for Residential Environment

Since this study addresses the emergence of new B5G-based applications with high QoS and massive connectivity requirements, we introduce the site-specific channel simulator [20], which is used to develop channel models for high data rate B5G indoor communication systems based on the advanced ray-tracing method.

The channel modeling approach consists of three main steps. First, a 3D platform is created that precisely defines the size and shape of the indoor environment, the reflection properties of the surface materials, and the specifications of the light sources and detectors (i.e., field of view (FOV), viewing angle, etc.). The CAD objects such as people and furniture, are also integrated into the 3D platform. Second, non-sequential ray-tracing in Zemax[®] is used to calculate the received optical power and the traversing length from the light source to the photodetector (PD). It is worth noting that the ray emission from the light source follows a certain statistical distribution that depends on the type of the source. The emitted rays are then traced through the traversing path until they are received by the PD. The received rays can be either the line-of-sight (LoS) components or the reflections from the walls, ceiling, floor and furniture in the indoor environment. The number of reflections is set via “Relative Minimum Intensity”. For example, if this parameter is set to 10^{-5} , this approach will be executed until the ratio between the intensity of the received ray

and the transmitted ray is 10^{-5} . The advanced ray-tracing method used then produces an output file containing the received power and traversing length of each ray. This data is processed by MATLAB[®] and the CIR can then be retrieved as [25]

$$h(t) = \sum_{i=1}^{N_r} P_i \delta(t - \tau_i), \quad (1)$$

where P_i is the optical power of the i th ray, τ_i is the propagation time of the i th ray, $\delta(t)$ is the Dirac delta function and N_r is the number of rays received at the detector. The ray-tracing approach used in this study for channel modeling was endorsed by the IEEE 802.15.7r1 and IEEE 802.11bb Task Groups for evaluating VLC system proposals [6, 26]. In addition, the non-sequential ray-tracing approach has been validated by a measurement campaign and shown that the channel models created using this approach agree well with the measurements [27, 28].

We adopt the practical considerations of the IEEE 802.11bb reference scenarios [29]. This standardization task group has defined wireless connectivity limited coverage where users can run a mix of applications such as Internet access and online video chat without worrying about the wireless signal penetrating to other locations. In this context, we consider a residential environment shown in Fig. 2 which includes a living room, a bedroom, a kitchen, a bathroom, and a corridor. Six users (i.e., PD locations) are considered within the apartment, namely two users in the living room, one user in the corridor, one user in the kitchen and two users in the bedroom. The PD locations are denoted as D_n , $n = 1, 2, \dots, 6$ (see Fig. 2a). The FOV and area of the detectors are 85° and 1 cm^2 , respectively. For standing users (D_2, D_3, D_4, D_6), the cell phone is held in the hand next to the ear and the PD is located on the top edge of the phone at a height of 1.8 m with a 45° rotation upward toward the ceiling (see Fig. 2b). For seated users (D_1 and D_5), the cell phone is held in the hand above the abdomen and the PD is located on the top edge of the phone at a height of 1.1 m with a 45° rotation upward toward the ceiling (see Fig. 2b). The details of the surfaces, objects and users within the platform can be found in Table 1. It should be noted, of course, that although specular reflections from a mirror or other shiny object may occur, most reflections are typically diffuse in nature, and most are well modelled as Lambertian [30].

There are 16 LED luminaires in the apartment. These are denoted by S_m , $m = 1, 2, \dots, 16$ (cf. Fig. 2a). The number of luminaires in each room and their power can be found in Table 2. The

(a)

(b)

Figure 2: (a) Residential scenario under consideration, and (b) location of PDs

LED luminaires used in the simulations are commercially available from Cree[®](CR6-800L). The average illumination level for general lighting in home environments at a height of 0.8 m is 150 lx [6]. The illumination level depends on the properties of luminaire, such as the light output, the size of fixture and the arrangement of the luminaires on the ceiling (i.e., number of luminaires, distance between them, etc.). The spatial distributions of illumination levels for living room, corridor, kitchen and bedroom are calculated and shown in Fig. 3. On these basis, the average, maximum, and minimum illumination levels are listed in Table 2. In addition, uniformity, defined as the ratio of minimum illuminance to average illuminance, with the ideal value of one and the typical value of more than 0.5 [6] is listed in Table 2.

Table 1: Specifications of user models and man-made objects within the residential environment

Living Room		Corridor	
Walls	Plaster	Walls	Plaster
Ceiling	Plaster	Ceiling	Plaster
Floor	Pinewood	Floor	Pinewood
Windows Frame	Aluminum	Door	Pinewood
Windows	Glass	Bedroom	
Table	Pinewood	Walls	Plaster
Floor Lamps	Aluminum	Ceiling	Plaster
Sofas	Cotton	Floor	Pinewood
TV	Black Paint	Windows Frame	Aluminum
Curtains	Cotton	Windows	Glass
Drawer	Pinewood	Doors	Pinewood
Carpet	Absorbing	Curtains	Cotton
Kitchen		Cooler	Steel Metal
Walls	Plaster	Bed	Cotton
Ceiling	Plaster	Drawer	Pinewood
Floor	Marble	TV	Black Paint
Cabinet	Pinewood	Users	
Oven	Steel Metal	Shoes	Black Piant
Sink	Steel Metal	Head and Hands	Absorbing
Countertop	Marble	Clothes	Cotton
Refrigerator	Steel Metal	Cell Phones	Black Paint

Based on the simulation scenario described above, we obtain a total of 54 CIRs. Let $h_{S_m D_n}$ denote the CIR between S_m and D_n . As shown in Fig. 2a, the CIRs can be divided into two groups. The first group consists of those in the living room, kitchen, and corridor, i.e., $h_{S_m D_n}$, $m = 1, \dots, 11$, $n = 1, \dots, 4$. The second group consists of those in the bedroom, i.e., $h_{S_m D_n}$, $m = 12, \dots, 16$, $n = 5, 6$. We present 16 sample CIRs in Fig. 4. For example, let us consider the CIR $h_{S_8 D_2}$. The CIR consists mainly of the LoS component only. This is because the S_8 luminaire placed in the corridor is located above the photodetector D_2 . On the other hand, $h_{S_9 D_2}$ is a multipath CIR with no LoS component. This is because the S_9 luminaire which is located in the corridor, is not in the FOV of the photodetector D_2 . As another example, we consider $h_{S_5 D_2}$. It contains both LoS and multipath components. Since the distance between the S_5 luminaire and the photodetector D_2 is large, the LoS amplitude is relatively small compared to that in $h_{S_8 D_2}$.

Table 2: Illumination levels for scenario under consideration

	Living Room	Corridor	Kitchen	Bedroom
Number of luminaires	6	3	2	5
Power of luminaire (W)	9	7.5	6.5	7.5
Average illumination (lx)	164.81	155.29	151.23	161.19
Maximum illumination (lx)	201.60	183.50	167.50	200.30
Minimum illumination (lx)	116.50	111.90	112.90	97.51
Illumination uniformity	0.70	0.72	0.74	0.60

4. Adaptive Transmission System Model

Considering the channel models presented in the previous section, in this section we discuss the physical (PHY) layer techniques that can be considered for IEEE 802.11bb [6]. Since the standards address the targeted peak data rates of up to 10 Gbps, OFDM has been proposed in [31] to mitigate ISI for the frequency-selective VLC channels. However, it should be noted that certain modifications are required to ensure that the signal is real and non-negative to establish optical OFDM. Several OFDM variants have been presented in the literature such as DCO-OFDM, ACO-OFDM, asymmetrically clipped DC-biased optical orthogonal frequency division multiplexing (ADO-OFDM), enhanced unipolar (eU)-OFDM, and reverse polarity optical (RPO)-OFDM. In the IEEE standardization work [31], DCO-OFDM is adopted as the mandatory waveform. In this work, we choose DCO-OFDM for the proposed adaptive transmission because the impairments due to the nonlinearity of LED are more pronounced in DCO-OFDM due to the high peak-to-average power ratio (PAPR) [32]. Therefore, DCO-OFDM is ideal for performance evaluation in a worst-case scenario.

Moreover, the VLC channel is deterministic, while the spatial characteristics vary significantly. Therefore, it is necessary to propose a link adaptation in which transmission parameters such as modulation order and transmit power are selected based on the channel conditions. To this end, we propose an adaptive BER-based modulation order switching scheme to maximize the data rate. We assume that 2-PSK (phase shift keying) and M-QAM (M -ary quadrature amplitude modulation) modulation schemes are available.

To transmit the signal of m^{th} LED, the DCO-OFDM technique assigns the complex symbols to

Figure 3: Spatial distributions of illumination levels for (a) living room, (b) corridor, (c) kitchen, and (d) bedroom

all odd and even subcarriers as [33]

$$\mathbf{X}_m = [0 \ x_1 \ x_2 \ \dots \ x_{N/2-1} \ 0 \ x_{N/2-1}^* \ \dots \ x_2^* \ x_1^*]^T, \quad (2)$$

where N is the number of subcarriers. \mathbf{X}_m is the input of the inverse discrete Fourier transform (IDFT), which has Hermitian symmetry to ensure that the output of the IDFT is real-valued. The

Figure 4: Sample CIRs

output of IDFT can be written as

$$x_m [n] = \frac{1}{\sqrt{N}} \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} X_m [k] e^{\frac{2\pi jnk}{N}}, \quad (3)$$

where $n = \{0, 1, \dots, N - 1\}$ and $X_s[k]$ is the k^{th} element of the vector \mathbf{X}_m of size N . Moreover, to avoid ISI, a cyclic prefix of length N_{CP} is appended to the beginning of $x_m[n]$. Then, the DC bias of B_{DC} is added to $x_m[n]$ to make it unipolar, which is another constraint of IM/DD. Therefore, the continuous waveform in the time domain $x_m(t)$ can be written as

$$x_m(t) = \sum_{n=0}^{L-1} x_m[n] \delta(t - nT_s) + B_{DC}, \quad (4)$$

where $L = N + N_{CP}$ is the total length of the OFDM symbol with appended cyclic prefix and T_s is the sampling interval. Then the received signal at the destination can be written as

$$y(t) = R \sqrt{\frac{P_X}{M}} \sum_{m=1}^M f(x_m(t)) \otimes h_m(t) + w(t), \quad (5)$$

where P_X is the total electrical OFDM signal power, M is the number of LEDs, R is the responsivity of the photodetector and $w(t)$ is the additive white Gaussian noise (AWGN) with zero mean and variance of σ_N^2 . Here, $h_m(t)$ denotes the band-limited electrical CIR defined in (1). The LED nonlinearity is modeled according to a Rapp model expressed as

$$f(x) = \frac{x}{\left(1 + \left|\frac{x}{x_{sat}}\right|^{2p}\right)^{\frac{1}{2p}}}, \quad (6)$$

where p denotes the parameter controlling the severity of the nonlinearity and x_{sat} denotes the saturation voltage.

At the receiver, the signal is converted to parallel streams and the cyclic prefix is removed. The receiver performs a N -point discrete Fourier transform (DFT) operation and obtains the complex-valued symbols in the frequency domain. The signal on the k^{th} subcarrier at the output of N -DFT can be written as

$$Y[k] = R \sqrt{\frac{P_X}{M}} \sum_{m=1}^M f(X_m[k]) H_m[k] + W[k], \quad (7)$$

where $H_m[k]$ and $W[k]$ are the k^{th} element of N -DFT of $h_m(t)$ and $w(t)$, respectively.

At the receiver, we denote the detector weights by $\mathbf{\Omega}$ acting on the hyperparameter-free feature maps of the observations $Y[k] \in \mathbb{R}^{n_G}$, $\Psi_{\alpha,\beta}([k]) : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{n_G}$, denoted as [22]

$$\Psi_{\alpha,\beta}(Y[k]) = \sqrt{\frac{2}{n_G}} \cos(\text{diag}[\boldsymbol{\alpha}]Y[k] + \boldsymbol{\beta}), \quad (8)$$

where \mathbf{Y} is a Gaussian matrix with standard normal rows, \mathbf{S} is uniformly distributed between $[0, 2\pi]$, and $\text{diag}[\cdot]$ denotes a diagonal matrix with entries from $[\cdot]$. Moreover, the elements of the vector $\boldsymbol{\varkappa} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_G}$ are drawn from the square-root of Gamma distributed random variables, $\sqrt{\Gamma[\alpha, \beta]}$, whose values are given as follows

$$\alpha = \frac{MN}{2}, \beta = \frac{\sigma_y^2}{2\pi^2\alpha}. \quad (9)$$

To unwarped $Y[k]$, the following reference signal is used using the pilots $X_{\text{pilots}}[k]$, and the channel-estimates, $\hat{H}_m[k]$

$$Y[k] = R \sqrt{\frac{P_X}{M}} \sum_{m=1}^M X_{\text{pilots}}[k] \hat{H}_m[k] + W[k]. \quad (10)$$

This reference signal enables hyperparameter-free unwarping of $Y[k]$ based on the minimum mean squared error cost-function, J_{mmse} , which is expressed as

$$J_{\text{mmse}} = \mathbb{E}[Y[k] - \boldsymbol{\Omega}^T \boldsymbol{\Psi}_{\alpha\beta}(Y[k])]^2, \quad (11)$$

where $\mathbb{E}[\cdot]$ denotes the statistical expectation, and the corresponding optimal weights are denoted as $\boldsymbol{\Omega}^*$, which is given by

$$\boldsymbol{\Omega}^* = \arg \min_{\boldsymbol{\Omega}} J_{\text{mmse}}, \quad (12)$$

and the unwarped weights observations are given as

$$\hat{Y}_{\text{unwarped}}[k] = \boldsymbol{\Omega}^{*T} \boldsymbol{\Psi}_{\alpha\beta}(Y[k]). \quad (13)$$

The received signal in (6) is optimally determined by the maximum likelihood (ML) decision rule which is expressed by

$$\hat{X} = \arg \min_{X[k] \in M\text{-ary}} \left\| \hat{Y}_{\text{unwarped}}[k] - RX[k] \sum_{m=1}^M H_m[k] \right\|^2, \quad (14)$$

where M is the modulation size. Therefore, the electrical SNR in k^{th} subcarrier can be written as

$$\text{SNR}[k] = \frac{R^2 P_X}{M(\sigma_N^2 + \sigma_e^2)} \left| \sum_{m=1}^M H_m[k] \right|^2, \quad (15)$$

where σ_e^2 is an approximation-error scaling with $O\left(\frac{1}{n_G}\right)$ even for the hyperparameter-free RFF used in this work for DCO-OFDM [22]. It is indeed noteworthy that the proposed contribution achieves results comparable to works as in [34] without depending on the choice of an appropriate value for the kernel width. In this context, deriving a suitable value of α , β for DCO-OFDM in (9) is an important secondary contribution of this paper. The subcarrier based BER for 2-PSK and M -QAM can be calculated by [33]

$$\text{BER}_{\text{SC}} [k] \approx \left\{ \begin{array}{ll} Q\left(\sqrt{2 \text{SNR}[k]}\right) & 2 - \text{PSK} \\ \frac{2(\sqrt{M}-1)}{\sqrt{M} \log_2 \sqrt{M}} Q\left(\sqrt{\frac{3 \text{SNR}[k]}{M-1}}\right) & \text{square } M - \text{QAM} \\ \frac{2}{\log_2(U \times J)} \left[\frac{U-1}{U} Q\left(\sqrt{\frac{6 \text{SNR}[k]}{U^2+J^2-2}}\right) + \frac{J-1}{J} Q\left(\sqrt{\frac{6 \text{SNR}[k]}{U^2+J^2-2}}\right) \right] & \text{rectangular } M = U \times J - \text{QAM} \end{array} \right\} \quad (16)$$

Then, the total BER can be calculated by averaging the BER values on each subcarrier as

$$\text{BER} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_k \text{BER}_{\text{SC}} [k]. \quad (17)$$

Through adaptive transmission, the receiver first calculates the instantaneous SNR per subcarrier. It should be noted that the receiver's SNR estimates are sent as feedback to the transmitter. In this context, either a RF-link or a LED-transmitter with a different color/wavelength can be used to separate the uplink and downlink communication channels and achieve bidirectional communication [35]. Apart from this, one can also use time-division duplexing (TDD) as described in [36]. This relaying process is not expected to be error-free. As part of our future work, these errors can be mitigated by advanced lookup table designs using variants of adaptive vector quantization methods. The receiver then determines the maximum constellation size on each subcarrier while satisfying a predefined target BER. The selection of the maximum constellation size is described in Algorithm 1. Finally, the data rate can be calculated as

$$R = \frac{1}{T_s} \frac{N/2 - 1}{L} \log_2 M \quad \text{bit/sec (bps)}. \quad (18)$$

First, we illustrate the averaged BER performance comparison over all cells in Fig. 5, and for DCO-OFDM we present the hyperparameter-free unidirectional downlink post-distortion for different subcarrier numbers of DCO-OFDM. In addition, the presented simulation study is repeated

Algorithm 1 Pseudo-code of maximum constellation size selection

```
1: Initialize: Set  $M = 2$  for all subcarriers
2: Starting algorithm:
3: for each  $k$  in  $1, 2, \dots, N/2 - 1$  do
4:   for each modulation order in given set do
5:     if  $\text{SNR}[k] \geq$  required SNR to satisfy given PER target then
6:       Set  $M$  with this modulation order;
7:     else if  $\text{SNR}[k] <$  required SNR to satisfy given PER target and  $M > 2$  then
8:       Set  $2^{\lceil \log_2(M)-1 \rceil}$  with this modulation order;
9:     else
10:      Stop iterations.
11:    end if
12:  end for
13: end for
```

over a series of trials to illustrate the consistency of hyperparameter selection in (9) for 256, 512 and 1024 subcarriers. For this exercise, the SNR was fixed at 10 dB without loss of generality. Based on these results, we can conclude that the RFF-based post-distorters offer a significant performance advantage. From Fig. 5, we can also see the generalization and consistency of the hyperparameter-free RFF across different subcarriers and across all experiments with the sampling parameter values proposed in (9).

Now we evaluate the performance improvement by using the adaptive transmission method with this hyperparameter-free postdistorter for DCO-OFDM. For 5G indoor services, we consider three types of VR and HD video services shown in Table 3 [5, 37–41]. We considered both data rate and service requirements for the services. Data rate refers to the amount of video or audio bits transmitted or processed per unit time and is used to measure video or audio quality. Note that in addition to data rate requirements, packet loss also has an important impact on service performance and multimedia application quality. The simulation parameters are also summarized in Table 4. Note that based on Table 3, we choose a packet loss error rate (PER) target of 10^{-9}

Figure 5: Demonstration of hyperparameter-free post-distortion for DCO-OFDM with the hyperparameter choices as per (9)

Table 3: 5G indoor services' data rate and packet loss requirements [5, 37–41]

Service		Data Rate (Mbps)	Packet Loss Error Rate
VR	Pre-VR	25	2.4×10^{-4}
	Entry-Level	100	2.4×10^{-5}
	Advanced	419	10^{-6}
HD Videos	Quasi 4K Video	30	5×10^{-4}
	UHD 4K Video	50	5×10^{-5}
	8K Video	100	10^{-9}

in our simulations to satisfy all services. Since one of the main contributions of this study is to design a communication system that balances the service requirements of 5G indoor services (i.e., VR, HD, etc.) for both data rate and packet loss, we consider the worst-case scenario in terms of packet loss (i.e., the target value $PER = 10^{-9}$) belonging to the 8K video service. If the service requirement of this application can be satisfied, the other services listed in Table 3 can also be served in the considered scenario. The relationship between BER and PER is given as

$$PER = 1 - (1 - BER)^q, \quad (19)$$

where q is the number of bits in a packet (including payload and complete medium access control (MAC) and PHY overhead) [42]. Since we assume no forward error correction (FEC) or automatic repeat request (ARQ) in our case, the packet loss rate is equal to PER.

Fig. 6a shows the PER values of different modulation orders for each PD location, where the

Table 4: Simulation parameters

Parameters	Values
Number of subcarrier (N)	1024[33]
Cyclic prefix length (N_{CP})	48[33]
Sampling interval (T_s)	10 ns
LED turn-on voltage level	2.75 V[33]
LED max-allowed voltage level	4 V[33]
DC-bias voltage	0.625 V[33]
Responsivity of PD (R)	0.28 A/W
Electrical transmit power (P_X)	-20 dBm
Power spectral density of noise	10^{-22} W/Hz
Target PER	10^{-9} [38, 39]

target PER is marked with a thick dashed line and the linear LED is assumed. From Fig. 6a, we can see that for each PD location, relatively highest modulation order that satisfies the target PER of 10^{-9} is chosen. In fact, the modulation orders 128-QAM, 2048-QAM, 4-QAM, 512-QAM, 64-QAM, and 16-QAM are selected for PD locations of PD1, ..., PD6, respectively. The achieved rates with adaptive transmission and non-adaptive transmission are shown in Fig. 6b. As a benchmark, we also included the results for the linear LED with the proposed adaptive transmission. From Fig. 6b, it can be seen for a linear channel and hyperparameter-free mitigation with adaptive transmission, peak rates of 524.4 Mbps and 333.7 Mbps are achieved respectively, while a non-adaptive system with the design of 2-PSK provides only 47.7 Mbps over all PD location indexes. These results show that all required data rates for 5G indoor high data rate services such as VR and HD videos are achieved by adaptive transmission, but only a subset of these services such as Pre-VR and Quasi-4K Video can be achieved by non-adaptive transmission.

5. Conclusion

In this paper, an adaptive data transmission algorithm for VLC systems was derived to meet the high data rate requirements of 5G indoor applications such as VR and HD videos. First, the channel was modelled by realistic ray-tracing, where the specifications of the user model and man-made objects were fully integrated into the channel model and the illumination requirements were also met. Realistic assumptions such as wavelength-dependent reflection properties, diffuse-

(a)

(b)

Figure 6: (a) PER results with respect to different modulation orders and (b) adaptive/non-adaptive transmission data rates for individual PDs

specular reflections, measured light sources, and reflection order up to 10 were also considered. Simulations were then performed for these channels to validate the proposed hyperparameter-independent SNR-adaptive transmission technique in the presence of LED nonlinearity. It was

found that the proposed method provides lower PER and higher data rates than other non-adaptive transmission methods without scenario-dependent hyperparameters, which makes the proposed link adaptation technique feasible for enabling VLC-based indoor services for upcoming B5G applications.

Acknowledgements

This work was supported by the Generalitat de Catalunya [grant number 2017 SGR 1195] and the national program on equipment and scientific and technical infrastructure under the European Regional Development Fund (FEDER) [grant number EQC2018-005257-P].

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